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Review Article

Rediscovering God through Science

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McHargue, Mike (2017). *Finding God in the Waves: How I Lost My Faith and Found It Again Through Science*. New York: Convergent. Pp. 224. ISBN: 978-1-47365-369-6

Mike McHargue is a public educator trusted by millions to use empathy and deep scientific insights to help them navigate some of the most difficult experiences of people. He's the host of "Ask Science Mike," co-founded the chart-topping show "The Liturgists Podcast," is the bestselling author of *You're a Miracle (and a Pain in the Ass)* (2020). He works as a science advisor and story consultant for film and television working with clients including Marvel Studios and Pete Holmes.

McHargue has been featured in *The Atlantic*, *The New York Times*, *The Washington Post*, *NPR* and numerous other publications. He is a well-known speaker. Mike lives in Los Angeles, CA, USA with his wife Jenny and daughters Madison and Macey.

Introducing the Book

Reading this incredible and inspiring book is one of the best things to happen to progressive Christianity and to anyone who is wondering how (or if) they can be a person of faith in an intellectual, modern world that seems like it's leaving mainstream Christianity behind (LeFever 2016).

The target audience for this book is probably not firmly committed Christians - in fact, McHargue pulls so few punches in describing his journey into atheism that this book trigger a collapse of faith in a typical evangelical reader. “The first half is raw and unflinching, and if you stopped reading there, it would be more effective than Dawkins' *The God Delusion* because it presents the same information with none of the arrogant condescension. If you had never been exposed to these arguments before, they could wreck you,” (LeFever 2016).

The second half, in which McHargue uses cosmology, neuroscience, and empirical data to try and put his broken faith back together again, is handled with honesty and transparency. His work on the podcasts "Ask Science Mike" and "The Liturgists" has already been profoundly influential on many and has prepared him to write this book.

This book does not support either “pompous, contempt-filled atheists” or “anti-intellectual, backwards-thinking Christians.” It contains “a fair-handed, even examination of both sides and then a possible middle path.” This book is a contribution to a liberal and progressive church trying to balance faith and intellect (LeFever 2016).

Faith and Science

How does science affect our faith? Truly it is a question facing millions today, as science reveals a Universe that's self-creating, as American culture departs from Christian social norms, and the idea of God begins to seem implausible at best or even barbaric at worst.

Mike McHargue understands the pain of gradual unfolding of faith. In *Finding God in the Waves*, he tells the story of how his Evangelical faith dissolved into atheism as he studied the Bible, a crisis that threatened his life, his friendships, and even his marriage. Years later, Mike was standing on the shores of the Pacific Ocean when a bewildering, seemingly mystical moment motivated him to take another look. But this time, it wasn't faith or scripture that led him back to God. It was truly inspired by science! (Inge 2018).

In *Finding God in the Waves*, "Science Mike" draws on his personal experience to tell the unbelievable story of how the latest research in neuroscience, cosmology, and physics led him back to faith. Among other revelations, we learn what brain scans reveal about what happens when we pray; how fundamentalism affects the psyche; and how God is revealed not only in scripture, but in the night sky, in subatomic particles, and in us (Inge 2018).

For the faithful and sceptic alike, *Finding God in the Waves* is a "winsome, lucid, page-turning read about belonging, life's biggest questions, and the hope of knowing God in an age of science" (Inge 2018). It is focussed and objective.

The book is essentially a personal testimony, an account of the loss and rediscovery of faith. The title is rather deceptive, though, since what seems to have brought him back to faith was not science, but a mystical experience every bit as profound and mysterious as that of Saul on the Damascus road. His rediscovery was made through science, not by science. His account of this is fascinating. He then goes on to seek to make sense of that experience through science. There's a noble tradition of that: it's Anselm's *fides quaerens intellectum*, faith seeking understanding (Inge 2018).

McHargue’s use of science is sensible, helpful, and at times, moving. For example, when he talks of what scientists refer to as the Initial Singularity, just before the Big Bang, in which everything which was to be was contained, he acknowledges: “I was there in that Singularity, as were all my ancestors and descendants. Every star that’s been born, every star that has died, was there, too. So was every particle that makes up every atom in the universe. All was there, together, in the beginning” (McHargue 2017). He adds that when he thinks of the Singularity, he thinks of God. And of himself (Inge 2018).

The Bible and Science

Some of the difficulties that he still has is connected with the Bible. For example, the inerrancy rather than the divine inspiration of the scriptures, and an insistence that penal substitution is the only and exclusive proper way of understanding the atonement (Inge 2018)

The Bible is a big part of why Mike lost his faith, which is actually a common phenomenon today. Referring to his early life, Mike describes the Bible this way: “I believed the Bible was inspired and inerrant, which is Baptist-ese for saying that God wrote the Bible, and, therefore, it is perfect. In this way of thinking, the Bible is accurate in whatever it talks about, including science and history.”

This led him to read the Bible four times in one year and he began to question its inerrancy (Demme 2016). He “noticed that Genesis 1 says trees were made before the stars.” This was a problem for Science Mike because, as he explains it, “Genesis says we were formed from dust, but cosmology tells us that you don’t get dust—unless you have stars first. Without dust, you don’t have the material to make trees or humans. There were no trees in our universe before there were stars” (McHargue 2017).

From his study of astronomy, physics, and other scientific details he knew that the order of Creation in Genesis and modern scientific understanding did not agree (Demme 2016). As Mike’s capacity to accept biblical inerrancy lowered, so did his belief in God.

In the face of unscientific statements in the Bible, something had to give. Instead of holding on to what he knew about God while letting go of what he knew about the Bible, Mike had to let go of it all; for him they were one and the same (Demme 2016).

God Encounter

But God was waiting for him. Through a series of mystical encounters and uncompromising love from his family, Mike experienced God again. It's not that God was ever lost, but Mike's ability to acknowledge and receive God turned off for a period of time.

In our modern, scientific world, we tend to view our beliefs as a set of ideas, which means we often associate mastery of a subject with people who can best articulate the ideas behind their beliefs. (McHargue 2017). But when we scan the brains of believers, we find that their understanding of God is nonverbal, more like a feeling or experience than a set of ideas. This is why Christians are usually stumped if someone asks them, "What is God?" "Contrary to what some skeptics say, it's not because these people's belief system is unsophisticated or simplistic. Instead it's that their experiences with God aren't primarily associated with the language center of the brain" (McHargue 2017). According to him trying to describe God is a lot like trying to describe falling in love

At the same we are not absolutely certain! He acknowledges that he still has doubts. Faith without doubt to accompany it is not faith at all, but knowledge. We are not given knowledge in this world; for now we see through a glass darkly. Physicists have had to learn to embrace uncertainty, and so must people of faith (Inge 2018).

Concluding Remarks

As someone who wants to help people see the Bible as manageable and meaningful, Mike's journey has been fascinating and creative. It challenges both believers and non-believers to take religion seriously and science too.

This book has numerous positive dimensions. One of them is to acknowledge that there are very good on the other side too. He dispels the myth, for example, that fundamentalist Christians are mad or bad. He makes clear that the fundamentalist Baptists from whom he eventually felt it necessary to withdraw were good, godly, loving, and caring people. That has been my experience of fundamentalists with whom I have come into contact through my late wife, Denise, who grew up as one (Inge 2018).

For anyone struggling to reconcile faith and science, this is a beautiful half-memoir, half-science book that has already made a contribution to the public discourse on science and religion dialogue.

On this whole this is a thoughtful, honest, and wise book. In this book. In this valuable book Mike exposes, in fact, his own vulnerability and authenticity as he shares his personal story. This book is also very readable. The science parts were accessible, easy to understand, and downright fascinating. As for the religion part Mike accepts the Bible, without requiring it to be a perfect text.

For anyone struggling to reconcile faith and science, this is a beautiful half-memoir, half-science book that has already made a contribution to the public discourse on science and religion dialogue. This book opens us to the uncertainties in both science and religion! We can hope for a similar refreshing treatment in his next book (McHargue, 2020).

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